

ELECTROSPUN NANOFIBROUS INTERLEAVES FOR IMPROVING THE PERMEABILITY RESISTANCE OF CRYOCYCLED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Interleaving is a common technique used to provide localised toughening in laminated composites, improving impact and fatigue damage resistance. However, little research has explored their effectiveness in cryogenic conditions, especially under cyclic loadings. This study presents an integrated experimental and numerical approach to evaluate the capability of ultra-thin electrospun veils in delaying the onset of localised delamination areas formed at crack junctions in cryogenically cycled laminates. Cross-ply laminates were interleaved with five-micron-thick veils at each asymmetric interface and cryogenically cycled. An indirect assessment of the degree of damage was carried out by measuring the helium permeability coefficients, and the crack networks were examined using micro-computed tomography scanning and scanning electron microscopy techniques. Compared to the baseline laminates, the sudden increase in permeability after cryocycling was damped in toughened laminates, yielding a lower coefficient by one order of magnitude after the first cryo-cycle and 40% after the second cycle. A finite element modelling approach with an integrated 3-D cohesive network was used to simulate the progressive discrete crack damage in cross-ply laminates subjected to cyclic thermomechanical loading. When the thermomechanical loading is high, the interleaves will show more resistance to damage growth due to their substantial R-curve effect. When the cyclic loads are low, the damped interfaces will tend to fatigue faster because of the increased stress from resisting the opening of transverse cracks. This work can be forecasted to assess the veil's performance in quasi-isotropic laminates with asymmetric interface angles and to explore the possibility of encapsulating nanofillers into the electrospun nanofibers to promote synergic toughening effects.

1 INTRODUCTION

The heterogeneous nature of composite laminates makes them susceptible to premature cracking due to the inherent mismatch in the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the composite constituents [1]. Fibre reinforcements have extremely small CTE, while matrix CTE is relatively larger. At cryogenic conditions, the fibres tend to expand slightly and the matrix attempts to contract, promoting thermal strains at the microscopic level. At the macroscopic scale, varying ply orientations lead to differential expansion in different directions, driven by the stiff fibres within each lamina. This differential expansion generates multiaxial thermal strains, causing the matrix to go into tension and, ultimately, the initiation of microcracks.

The developed microcracks do not have sufficient energy to break the fibres, so they propagate along them longitudinally and through the thickness of the lamina [2]. The microcracks get arrested as

they approach an interface with a dissimilar ply orientation. The tip of the arrested microcrack acts as a stress raiser and induces localised delamination at the interlaminar region. These zones are the junctions that interconnect the crack network, which has direct implications for the gas leakage rates through damaged laminates. This delamination area grows as the number of service cycles increases, and subsequently, the crack opening displacement (COD) increases, leading to higher gas leakage rates [3, 4]. Delaying the onset and growth of these localised delaminations will improve the gas barrier performance of linerless composite tanks [5].

Interleaving techniques are known to provide localised interlaminar toughening effects without necessarily compromising the laminate's global response [6, 7]. These processes involve placing additional layers of materials, usually made of soft thermoplastics, between the individual plies of the composite laminate. For instance, HexPly M21 and Toray 3900-2B prepregs were toughened with polyamide particles and used to build primary structures in Airbus A350 and Boeing 777 aircraft [8-10].

Overall, the effectiveness of the interleaves in enhancing damage resistance has been extensively demonstrated in impact and mechanical fatigue problems [11]. However, there is a lack of understanding and knowledge regarding their toughening effects at cryogenic temperatures, particularly compared to the toughness enhancements achieved with thermoplastic-thermoset blends. Further investigation is needed to understand their potential use for improving the delamination resistance in composite laminates for cryogenic applications.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Methodology

An epoxy resin system was used in this study, consisting of three components: bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA, Huntsman Araldite® LY1564), methyl tetrahydrophthalic anhydride curing agent (MTHPA, Huntsman Aradur® 917-1), and tertiary amine co-hardener (accelerator 960-1). For the manufacture of composite laminates, Torayca T300 CK-12 unidirectional carbon fibre reinforcement with an areal weight of 200 gsm was utilised. Polyethersulfone (PES, Ultrason® E1010 NAT, 1.37 g/cc, BASF-Germany) was selected as the thermoplastic toughening agent. An organic solvent, N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF, purity >99%), was used to synthesise the polymer solution for electrospinning, as demonstrated by [12]. During the electrospinning process, PES nanofibres were directly deposited onto a dry carbon fabric that was mounted onto the drum-collector. After the electrospinning process was completed, the fabric with the deposited PES nanofibres was dried in a vacuum chamber at 100 °C overnight to ensure the evaporation of any residual DMF solvent from the electrospun PES nanofibres.

Cross-ply composite laminates, having a layup sequence of $[0_3/90_3]_s$, were manufactured for a cryogenic cycling test. Two laminates were made, with and without electrospun PES veils. The toughened laminate was interleaved only at the 0/90 interfaces with a single five-micron-thick veil. The vacuum bag resin infusion technique was used to minimise the void content in the laminates. The laminate underwent curing in an ASC autoclave under an absolute vacuum pressure of negative 800 mbar inside the bag and atmospheric external pressure throughout the process. The curing schedule comprised three segments. Firstly, the laminate was dwelled at 60 °C for one hour to facilitate diffusion between the PES-veil and epoxy resin. During the second segment, the cross-linking reaction commenced as the temperature increased to 120 °C and was maintained for four hours. Finally, after consolidation, the temperature was gradually reduced to 50 °C at a rate of 5 °C per minute. The cured laminates were 250×250 mm² and 2.5 ± 0.04 mm thick. Each laminate was sectioned into four 100 mm squared samples with a diamond cut-off wheel on the Axitom-5TM from Struers.

The baseline and interleaved cross-ply samples were cryogenically cycled from room temperature to the liquid nitrogen (LN₂) temperature for five cycles to determine their resistance to microcracking. Direct submersion in LN₂ was avoided to minimise thermal shocks, and instead, the specimens were subject to a gradual three-stage precooling process. Initially, the specimens were placed in a freezer at -28 °C for at least an hour and then chilled at approximately -100 °C in a chamber containing LN₂ beneath the samples. After another hour, the samples were removed from the chamber and immediately immersed in LN₂ for 10 minutes. The reverse order of this process was followed for warming up the samples to room temperature. Finally, they were allowed to dry at 60 °C for two hours to remove condensed moisture before further cycling or permeability testing.

Permeability measurements are frequently used as a quantitative assessment of the progressive damage state in laminates [13, 14]. Permeability tests were performed to measure the helium leakage rates through the cross-ply laminates as a function of the number of cryogenic cycles. These tests were conducted at room temperature in compliance with the ISO 15105 standard for determining gas transmission rate (*GTR*) by the differential pressure method. The *GTR* can be expressed as a physical property, called the gas permeability coefficient (*P*), by taking its product with the average laminate thickness. It should be noted that *P* is commonly reported in the literature in metric units as standard cubic centimetres times metre per square metre times day times atmosphere (scc·m/m²·day·atm). The standard conditions for measuring the gas volume are set to room temperature and atmospheric pressure [14]. The ASTM D1434 provides multiple factor tables for converting the permeance or gas permeability from one unit system to another.

The *GTR* measurements were taken using the Manometric Permeability Meter Mk VI acquired from Versaperm. The equipment setup is illustrated in Figure 1. The cross-ply sample was mounted in a gas transmission cell between a pressurised chamber and a vacuumed downstream chamber. The gas transmission area was 1/200 m² and the testing temperature was set to 298 K. Helium gas permeated through the laminate from the high-pressure chamber to the downstream chamber. The rate of pressure increase in the downstream chamber was recorded every second. A moving average of 50 points was applied to reduce the noise in the test data. Each sample was tested under three different gas supply gauge pressures of 1, 2, and 3 bars in order to check the consistency of permeance measurement because of potential gas leakages from the barrier seals. Measurement time varied according to the leakage rate through the damaged laminates. All the runs were continued until the time limit of one thousand minutes was reached or the pressure build-up in the downstream chamber exceeded 900 mbar to avoid damaging the low-pressure transducer. The uncycled samples reached the time limit, whereas the cycled ones had higher leakage rates and met the second test stop criterion.

Figure 1: (a) Gas permeability tester and (b) the sample clamping fixtures located inside the temperature chamber.

Non-destructive X-ray micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) scanning is a 3-D visualisation technique that is used for the detection of internal damage in structures. Micro-CT imaging was conducted on the HeliScanTM microCT from ThermoFisher, which had a 160kV/16W Hamamatsu X-ray tube with diamond windows. The flatbed detector size was 3072×3072 pixels, and the readout rate was 3.75 fps. To achieve high voxel resolutions, down to one micron in size, the samples were carefully sectioned into small 3×3 mm pieces. This allows the sample to sit closer to the X-ray source for higher magnification. One sample was sectioned and inspected after one cryogenic cycle, and another sample after five cycles. Avizo software was used for image data processing, segmentation, and visualisation analysis.

Although the CT-scan voxel resolution was refined to detect the transverse microcracks, capturing the localised delaminations was challenging. The crack opening displacement of these delaminations was at sub-micron levels after the sample reached room temperature after cryogenic cycling. Therefore, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was primarily used to inspect the localised delaminations at the tips of the transverse cracks identified under the microscope. For SEM analysis, the sample's edge was coated with a 40 nm thick platinum layer, and then it was examined using the FEI Nova nanoSEM-230 equipment.

2.2 Helium permeability measurements

A comparison between the determined **GTR** of the baseline and interleaved laminates as a function of the number of cryogenic cycles is given in Figure 2(a). The presented **GTR** values were averaged between the samples of each set for each gas supply pressure. The **GTR** results are consistent between the different pressure levels, indicating no significant gas leakage from the transmission cell during the measurements. The highest standard deviation was 7.7×10^{-14} scc/m²·day·atm, which occurred for the uncycled specimens because the mean **GTR** was very low, making the measurements more sensitive to variation in specimen thicknesses. The **GTR** increased by two orders of magnitude after the first cryogenic cycle and systematically increased afterwards with subsequent cycles. The helium permeability coefficients of the baseline and interleaved samples are presented in Figure 2(b) versus the number of cryogenic cycles.

The permeability of uncycled samples from both sets measured a value of 8.1×10^{-16} scc·m/m²·day·atm, which is within the same range as the results reported in [15]. After the first cryogenic cycle, the permeability of the baseline samples increased by three orders of magnitude to 1.6×10^{-13} scc·m/m²·day·atm. In contrast, the interleaved laminates were one order of magnitude lower than the baseline, measuring 3.5×10^{-14} scc·m/m²·day·atm. Even after two cycles, the permeability of interleaved samples was 40.6% lower than the baseline value, measuring 1.7×10^{-13} versus 2.8×10^{-13} scc·m/m²·day·atm of the baseline.

The permeability of the baseline samples plateaus from the second cycle to roughly 3.4×10^{-13} scc·m/m²·day·atm. A 71% increase in permeability occurred in the fifth cycle, suggesting the potential initiation of a new crack. The permeability of interleaved samples plateaus as well from the third cycle and onwards to 2.2×10^{-13} scc·m/m²·day·atm. The error bars during this plateau overlap with those of the baseline samples. These results suggest that the interleaving technique damped damage evolution after onset during the initial stages of cryogenic cycling. With subsequent cyclic loadings, the damage reaches a saturation point in laminates with or without interleaves until a new crack forms, causing a sudden increase in the permeability coefficient. These observations are in agreement with those reported by Choi and Sankar [16], where the permeability of blocked [0/90]_s laminate increased by two orders of magnitude in the first cycle and remained constant afterwards till 20 cycles.

Figure 2: (a) The determined gas transmission rates (GTR) at three gas supply pressures (1-3 bars) as a function of cryogenic cycles, and (b) the corresponding average gas permeability coefficients of the baseline and interleaved cross-ply laminates.

2.3 Examination of the crack networks

Image processing was carried out to create a 3-D reconstruction of the laminate sample pieces and segment different phases within the structure, as shown in Figure 3. The network of polyester stitches was captured and illustrated in the figure. However, the attempt to reconstruct a similar network for the cracks was not successful because the crack opening displacements (CODs) were too small to trace fully. An example of a detected internal crack in a baseline laminate after one cryogenic cycle is illustrated in Figure 4. The voxel resolution of the scan was one micron. The maximum COD was determined to be $5.7\ \mu\text{m}$ under the SEM, and it was reduced to submicron at the initiation and arrestment stages of the crack, making it difficult to detect. In addition, the polyester stitches had significantly higher contrast than the fibres and the matrix, resulting in blurry voxels near the stitches due to beam hardening artifacts. Micro-CT scanning of carbon fibre-based laminates is generally known to be more challenging compared to other types of fibre reinforcements [17]. Therefore, the collected scan data was primarily used to detect the locations of the cracks and their propagation path.

Figure 3: 3-D reconstruction and segmentation of micro-CT scan images of a section of a baseline cross-ply sample.

Figure 4: A 2-D X-ray image of a sectioned piece of a baseline cross-ply laminate showing a single inner transverse crack.

The micro-CT scans of cryogenically cycled laminates reveal that cracks tend to initiate from voids and polyester stitches, as in the case in Figure 4. The extension of the cracks across the sample width followed the voids and was deflected around the stitches. The minimum spacing between two fully developed sequential cracks was considered for measuring the crack density. The spacing between the inner cracks was about two times higher than the outer cracks, measuring 1.36 and 3.38 mm, respectively. In contrast, a single inner crack was detected in a 7 mm long sample and no outer cracks. This is a significant increase in the crack density versus the number of cycles, and it explains the increase in the gas permeability in the baseline laminates at the fifth cycle. However, the permeability increase ratio between the uncycled laminates and those with one cycle is significantly higher. This suggests that the increase in the permeability is not solely proportional to the crack density, but potentially the existence of delaminations as well, which were not detected in the micro-CT scans.

Upon examination under the microscope and SEM analysis, short-length delaminations in samples after one and five cycles were observed. The onset of localised delaminations occurs when the tip of the transverse crack terminates at the interface. However, this is not always the case when the singular stress field in its vicinity is not intense enough to overcome the corrected critical fracture toughness, depending on the relative thicknesses between $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ [18]. The SEM micrograph in Figure 5 shows a transverse crack in an interleaved sample after one cycle. The crack initiated from the outer surface and propagated through a void located at a polyester stitch and arrested at the $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ interface. Similar crack arrestment behaviour was observed on baseline samples as well after one cryogenic cycle. Fibre breakage near the arrested crack tip in the neighbouring 0° ply was not observed as reported in similar studies in [18].

Figure 5: SEM micrograph of an interleaved sample after one cryogenic cycle, showing the initiation of a transverse crack from the outer laminate surface, its propagation through a void, and its arrestment at the interface of the adjacent ply.

Overall, no localised delaminations were observed to be induced from the tips of outer cracks, even after five cycles. For inner cracks, however, a few localised delaminations with random lengths were detected. The representative SEM micrographs in Figure 6 are of a baseline sample after five cycles, showing the branching of a transverse crack and propagating through the $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ interface. The delamination propagation path seems to follow the interface of fibre/matrix. Another behaviour was noticed and illustrated in Figure 6(b) where the crack branches out before approaching the $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ interface. The branched crack propagation eventually got arrested at the interface.

The process of developing these localised delaminations at the crack tips is thought to contribute to the slight increments in the gas permeability coefficient with repeated cycling after the initial cycle. However, the reason for the variation between the gas permeability trends of the baseline and interleave laminates was not clear after examining the cracks. The generation of transverse cracks was triggered by the voids, which caused a scatter in the crack densities observed between the samples. In

addition, delamination lengths were difficult to detect and quantify due to the inconsistency in their occurrence along the interfaces. This is a common challenge, and researchers tend to rely solely on counting the transverse cracks and measuring their opening displacement to explain differences in laminate permeability [13, 19]. Therefore, numerical modelling is generally used to analyse the evolution of interconnected crack networks and their potential effect on gas permeability [5, 20].

Figure 6: SEM micrographs of a baseline sample after five cryogenic cycles, showing (a) the transformation of a transverse crack into a localised delamination and (b) full arrestment of the transverse crack propagation at the interface. The crack in (b) branched out before approaching the interface.

3 NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION

3.1 Modelling approach

The ability to predict intraply discrete cracks, interlaminar delaminations, and their interactions is useful for analysing the possible ways to delay or suppress the damage in composite laminates. The cohesive network technique was employed to simulate progressive damage and map crack junctions for potential gas leakage routes. The model utilises the brick-and-mortar concept, originally proposed by Begley et al. [21], to simulate the initiation and diffusion of discrete cracks without the need to have a pre-crack. The bricks represent the continuum elements, and the cohesive elements (CEs) are regarded as the mortar.

The discrete crack locations must be predetermined to insert CEs along potential paths within continuum elements. These coordinates can be predetermined since matrix-dominant intralaminar cracks propagate along the fibre direction under thermomechanical cyclic loading. Fibre breakage appears as the final stage of failure only if the mechanical stresses are substantially high enough, causing the ultimate fracture of the structure [22]. In this study, fibre breakage was not considered a potential failure consequence of the presented thermomechanical loading case. The CEs were inserted parallel to the fibre orientation and at the interfaces to represent two premature failure modes, namely, transverse matrix cracking and interface delaminations. Contact connections were defined between adjacent strips and interlaminar regions to represent potential intralaminar cracks and delaminations, respectively. More details on the implementation of this approach and the cyclic bilinear cohesive zone model are presented in [23]. User-defined Python scripts were used within the Ansys pre-processor to automate the process of constructing a laminate model and integrating the network of CEs. A total of five Python scripts were coded to automate the process of embedding CEs within composite laminates in Ansys Mechanical software

The temperature-dependent mechanical properties and interface properties are given in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. These properties were obtained by calibrating simple coupon models against testing data presented in [12]. The interface properties of the interlaminar and intralaminar regions differ owing to the increased surface area of the intralaminar cracks as they deflect around the

randomly distributed fibres. For simplicity, they are commonly presumed to be identical [18]. Applying this assumption herein should not influence the conclusions of this study because the delaminations are under investigation, and the transverse interface properties are identical between baseline and interleaved models. It should also be noted that the effect of asymmetric interface angles on interlaminar fracture toughness was not considered because the collected test data is limited to unidirectional samples. This limitation is not expected to produce biased results towards one of the models, but it will affect the prediction accuracy. In reality, the interleaving technique shows better toughness improvements under mode I and mode II in woven composites than in unidirectional [24].

Description	Symbol	Value at 293 K	Value at 77 K	Units
Young's modulus	E_{11}	125	135	GPa
	$E_{22} = E_{33}$	9.09	9.57	GPa
Shear modulus	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	2.77	2.98	GPa
	G_{23}	1.10	1.20	GPa
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.34	0.34	-
	ν_{23}	0.48	0.48	-
Coefficients of thermal expansion	α_{11}	-0.06	-0.11	ppm/K
	$\alpha_{22} - \alpha_{33}$	29.3	23.98	ppm/K

Table 1: Material properties for T300/Araldite 1564/Aradur 917.

Cohesive property	Baseline laminate		Interleaved laminate		Units
	293 K	77 K	293 K	77 K	
<i>Intralaminar zones</i>					
σ_c	60.8	81.1	60.8	81.1	MPa
τ_c	62.6	99.3	62.6	99.3	MPa
G_{Ic}	0.19	0.18	0.19	0.18	kJ/m ²
G_{IIc}	0.85	0.91	0.85	0.91	kJ/m ²
<i>Interlaminar regions</i>					
σ_c	60.8	81.1	60.8	81.1	MPa
τ_c	62.6	99.3	62.6	99.3	MPa
G_{Ic}^{int}	0.19	0.18	0.19	0.18	kJ/m ²
G_{Ic}^{prop}	0.69	0.34	0.69	0.34	kJ/m ²
G_{IIc}^{ini}	0.85	0.91	0.85	0.91	kJ/m ²
G_{IIc}^{prop}	1.2	0	1.26	0	kJ/m ²
<i>Fatigue parameters</i>					
ε	0.09	0.45	0.1	0.5	
η	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	
p	2	2	2	2	

Table 2: Temperature-dependent intralaminar and interlaminar interface properties used in modelling.

3.2 A single transverse crack under uniaxial static loading

The cohesive properties, namely the interface strengths and the critical strain energy release rates, are expected to impact the initiation of matrix cracks and the onset of delaminations. This impact is sensitive to the thickness ratio of the 90° ply relative to the 0° plies, as suggested in [18]. To investigate these effects, a 3D FE model of a cross-ply laminate under uniaxial tension was developed. The model includes two pre-existing transverse cracks at each end and one prospective crack in the middle of the span length. Three symmetry planes were prescribed to reflect the following symmetries: through-thickness mid-plane (x-z) at the bottom surface of the 90° ply, longitudinal cross-sectional plane (x-y) on all the side faces, and transverse cross-sectional plane (z-y) on the face of the 0° ply. A

3% longitudinal tensile strain along the x-axis was prescribed onto the face of the 0° ply opposite the x-y symmetry plane. The ply size was 5×10 mm and 0.2 mm in thickness. Three layup sequences were modelled, having a different number of transverse plies, namely [90₂/0₂]_s, [90₄/0₂]_s, and [90₈/0₂]_s. The corresponding 90° block thicknesses (t_{90}) are 0.4, 0.8, and 1.6 mm. The intralaminar contact region was prescribed the neat interface properties, whereas three sets of interlaminar cohesive properties were defined: a) the neat properties, b) interleaved properties, and c) neat properties with a 50% increase in the interface strengths (σ_{nt} , τ_s).

The normal stresses in the 0° ply were three orders of magnitude higher than those generated in the 90° ply. Typical curves of the maximum normal stress and maximum in-plane shear stress in the laminate versus the applied longitudinal strain are given in Figure 7. The figure compares the laminate responses with the three different interlaminar contact properties. The laminate's initial linear behaviour corresponds to the elastic material properties. All curves show a small step at about 0.9% strain, and then the curve trends continue to increase linearly. This step corresponds to the initiation of the transverse crack. A shear-lag effect is observed owing to the presence of pre-cracks at the ends of the 90° ply. The thickness of the ply has a direct effect on the shear-lag distribution, where the thinner it is, the quicker the stress is transferred from the outer 0° ply to the 90° ply. The laminate configuration with the thickest transverse ply block requires higher applied strains to initiate transverse cracks. Therefore, under mechanical fatigue loadings, the characteristic crack density is expected to increase as the 90° decreases [22]. However, the normal stress severity increases in thinner transverse plies, meaning thicker blocks of transverse plies are more susceptible to microcracking at early loading stages, but the overall crack density is lowered with repeated loadings. For gas barrier applications, the use of alternating thin plies was recommended to delay the initiation of matrix cracking [16].

Figure 7: Typical curves of (a) the maximum normal stress and (b) the maximum in-plane shear stress in [90₈/0₂]_s laminate with different interface properties at the interlaminar region.

The subsequent failure after transverse cracking is the onset of delamination, which corresponds to the second step in Figure 7. The strain to onset delaminations is delayed, as shown on the laminate normal stress response in Figure 7(a). The normal stress kept rising linearly since the 0° ply still carried the loads elastically. The delamination lengths of the models with the three different sets of interlaminar properties are illustrated in Figure 8. The figure also compares the delaminations in [90₂/0₂]_s and [90₈/0₂]_s laminates for each interface property set. In all the models, the delamination onset began simultaneously from all three transverse cracks owing to the uniformity of the loading and geometry. The cohesive process zone of the interleaved model was the largest due to the higher critical toughness compared to the others, which, in turn, enlarges the cohesive zone envelope. The corresponding delamination length was 21% shorter than the reference neat model. The 50% increase in the neat interface strengths reduced the convergence efficiency of the model due to the narrower cohesive process zone. It also increased the delamination length by 14% compared to the neat model. The delamination propagation length and cohesive process length were insensitive to variations in the transverse ply thickness.

Figure 8: Top view of the models showing the sensitivity of the delamination area and process zone to the interlaminar cohesive properties relative to the min-max thicknesses of the transverse ply.

3.3 A cross-ply laminate under biaxial fatigue loading

Two $[0_3/90_3]_s$ laminate models were constructed, one with the baseline interlaminar interface properties and the second with interleaved properties. Since the mesh and contact patterns were uniform, the Gaussian (normal) distribution was used to randomise the interface strengths and the critical strain release energies, allowing the damage to onset at random locations, which was necessary to avoid convergence difficulties. Randomisation techniques are commonly employed to simulate multiple delaminations [5, 19]. To avoid creating biased results, the contact properties at each intralaminar contact region were identical between the baseline and interleaved models. The laminates were loaded for 15 cycles with a differential body temperature from 293 to 77 K. To accelerate the damage evolution, an equal biaxial tension strain of 0.1% was applied with a load ratio of 0.1. A dynamic viscous regulation coefficient of 1×10^{-3} to resolve convergence difficulties when encountered.

The predicted damage evolution in the baseline and interleaved laminates after 15 cycles is illustrated in Figure 9. After two cycles, the first fully developed matrix crack occurred in the 90° ply. The crack propagated through the thickness before extending rapidly across the width of the laminate. The initiation of this crack caused a relaxation in the 90° ply, and subsequently, the other intralaminar interfaces were undamaged. In contrast, four adjacent 0° interfaces were experiencing cohesive fatigue damage. The outer intralaminar interfaces tend to soften near the fully developed crack. The tip of a transverse crack acts as a stress raiser that triggers the formation of a stitch crack in the adjacent ply. The softening regions propagated transversely through the thickness before advancing longitudinally along fibres. That is, the energy release rate is twice as high in the transverse direction than in the longitudinal [25]. Such cracks are thin in nature, and they grow unstably in the transverse direction, quickly occupying the lamina's thickness [26]. After that, the partially developed 0° crack had no choice but to propagate longitudinally when the strain energy rate exceeded the critical fracture toughness.

Cohesive softening at the interlaminar region along the fully developed crack is observed in the enlarged image in Figure 9. The adjacent 0° ply resisted the crack openings of the damaged 90° lamina and produced high levels of interlaminar normal and shear stresses. These stresses were severe enough to overcome the interface strength of the interlaminar region. However, the energy release rate was not sufficient to onset delaminations. This explains the rare occurrence of localised delaminations at the crack tips of the laminates when examined under the SEM. The transverse matrix cracking pattern between the baseline and interleaved laminate was identical. A sudden increase in the damage occurred when the first transverse cracks initiated after two cycles. The toughened interface damped this jump in damage by 20.4% compared to the baseline. Both interfaces were linearly softening afterwards with subsequent cycling. The final damage value of the interleaved model was 16.1% lower than the reference. This indicates that the damage growth was higher in interleaved interfaces, which is

driven by the localised stress state. This stress severity was higher due to the damage effect while resisting the transverse crack opening displacements.

Figure 9: Predicted damage evolution in the baseline and interleaved cross-ply laminates. The enlarged region shows the softening of the interlaminar zone at the junction between two transverse cracks. The legend represents the damage parameter, where one means a fully damaged element.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effectiveness of the interleaving technique in minimising the interconnections in a crack network, and thus permeability coefficients, was explored in this study. Electrospun PES veils were used to toughen cross-ply laminates. Helium gas permeability rates through these laminates were measured as a function of the number of cryo-cycles. Compared to the baseline samples, the interleaving technique significantly reduced the permeability coefficient by one order of magnitude after the first cryo-cycle and by 40% after the second cycle. This suggests that the toughening effects seen in the coupon testing data have effectively reduced the crack network size. With subsequent loadings, the growth in the crack network reached a saturation point.

Examination of the cracks with micro-CT scanning and SEM techniques revealed that the inner plies had a higher crack density than the outer plies. Transverse cracks tend to extend from trapped voids in the matrix near the stitches, causing variability in crack density measurements. The majority of these cracks were arrested at the interface of the adjacent ply without branching into localised delaminations. The observed delaminations were short and random in their occurrence.

The finite element model was employed to provide a supporting analysis of these observations and to highlight the impact of the interleaving technique. The model demonstrated how PES veils delay the onset of delaminations and slow their growth rate. These effects were apparent in cross-ply laminates with multiple inner ply thicknesses. The improvement levels were consistent relative to the untoughened model as the ply thickness reduced. The onset of delamination was suppressed in all the models till a later stage of uniaxial loading when the 90° ply thickness reduces. The results from the gas permeability measurements and modelling predictions favour using the interleaving technique to improve the damage resistance in cryo-cycled laminates.

To summarise, the use of interleaves is beneficial in damping the initial evolution of damage networks. If the thermomechanical loading is high, the interleaves will show more resistance to damage growth due to their substantial R-curve effect, which was assessed experimentally in the previous chapters. When the cyclic loads are low, the damped interfaces will tend to fatigue faster because of the increase in the stress state from resisting the opening of transverse cracks.

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